

Effect of a Nurse-Led Interactive Education On Perceptions of Covid-19 Vaccine Among Nurses in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos

AUTHOR(S): NDURUE, Light Obioma (RN, MSN, OHSN, CPHN), OKAFOR, Ngozi Anthonia (RN, RM, RPHN, PhD), ABARIBE, Abaribe E. (RN, RM, RPHN, FWAPCNM, PhD), ABDULMALIK, Adams Adedayo (RN, RM, BNSc)

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of a nurse-led interactive education program on the perceptions of COVID-19 vaccines among nurses at Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), Nigeria. A quasi-experimental pre-/post-test one-group design was employed, involving 527 nurses. The study utilized a questionnaire assessing demographic profiles and perceptions toward vaccine safety. Validity and reliability of the instrument were established through face and content validity, as well as a pilot test with a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.88. Participants completed pre-test questionnaires, engaged in nurse-led interactive education sessions, and then completed post-test questionnaires. Statistical analysis revealed a significant increase in positive perceptions post-intervention, with mean perception scores rising from 36.8 ± 5.03 to 38.9 ± 3.63 . This shift suggests enhanced acceptance and understanding of COVID-19 vaccination among nurses following the intervention. The study underscores the efficacy of nurse-led educational initiatives in influencing perceptions and promoting COVID-19 vaccination uptake among healthcare professionals. Recommendations include the development of comprehensive educational programs and workshops targeting vaccine awareness among nurses, as well as increased investment in nurse-led interventions to enhance vaccine-related communication and address hesitancy.

Keywords: Nurse-Led Interactive Education, Perception, COVID-19 Vaccine, Nurses,

E.G.C.S.J

Accepted 25 February 2024
Published 28 February 2024
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14060008

**ABOUT
AUTHOR**

Author(s):

NDURUE, Light Obioma (RN, MSN, OHSN, CPHN)
Department of Public/Community Health Nursing,
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State

OKAFOR, Ngozi Anthonia (RN, RM, RPHN, PhD)
Department of Public/Community Health Nursing,
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State

ABARIBE, Abaribe E. (RN, RM, RPHN, FWAPCNM, PhD)
Department of Public/Community Health Nursing,
School of Nursing Science,
Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State

ABDULMALIK, Adams Adedayo (RN, RM, BNSc)
Lagos State University Teaching Hospital

Introduction

The advent of COVID-19 vaccines marked a pivotal moment in the pandemic narrative. Vaccination campaigns, aiming for widespread immunity, have become essential in curbing the virus's spread. However, hesitancy towards vaccines, fueled by safety concerns and misinformation, remains a barrier to achieving comprehensive vaccination coverage. This study stems from the urgent need to address these concerns, especially among healthcare workers, who are both vulnerable and essential in the fight against the virus (Osakinle et al., 2021).

The African continent has been one of the regions most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, with over 9 million confirmed cases and over 230,000 deaths reported (Ogunrinde & Gbenga-Epebinu, 2020). West Africa has experienced a significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, with Nigeria being the most affected country in the region. As of May 2023, Nigeria has recorded over 266,675 confirmed cases and over 3,155 deaths, (WHO, 2023). The rollout of COVID-19 vaccines in Africa has been slow, with access to vaccines being limited due to supply chain constraints and high level of vaccine hesitancy. Hence the urgent need to address perception of covid-19 vaccine (Blanchard et al., 2018).

In a study by Ogunrinde and Gbenga Epebinu (2020), COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy was reported among Nigerians. While Truong et al. (2021), find seven major factors that promote vaccine hesitancy or acceptance as demographic factors influencing vaccination (ethnicity, age, sex, pregnancy, education, and employment), accessibility and cost, personal responsibility and risk perceptions, other precautionary measures were taken based on the decision to vaccinate, trust in health authorities and vaccines, the safety and efficacy of a new vaccine, and lack of information or vaccine misinformation.

The rollout of COVID-19 vaccines in the country has been slow, with vaccine hesitancy being a significant challenge (Shah et al., 2021). Therefore, there is a need to address perception of covid-19 vaccine among Nurses and improve vaccine update among them among the Nigerian population. Nigeria has experienced a significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, with Lagos being the epicenter of the pandemic accounting for 35.4% of the pandemic in Nigeria (NCDC 2022). The Lagos State University Teaching Hospital (LASUTH), a crucial healthcare facility, catered to the affected population and frontline workers, including nurses who faced heightened exposure risks (Ajayi et al., 2020). The research assessed changes in Nurses' perceptions pre- and post-intervention. It scrutinized shifts in attitudes, beliefs, and understanding regarding COVID-19 vaccines among Nurses actively participating in the nurse-led interactive education.

This study evaluated the impact of a nurse-led interactive education program on perceptions of COVID-19 vaccines among Nurses at LASUTH, offering unique insights into nurses' views in Nigeria. The study specifically examined the pre and post intervention perceptions of COVID-19 vaccine among Nurses.

Methodology

The study used a quasi-experimental, pre-/post-test one-group design to assess the effect of nurse-led interactive education on perception of COVID-19 vaccine safety among nurses in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos, Nigeria. The study population consists of 527 nurses in LASUTH, Lagos state. Being nurses who were available during data collection in LASUTH. The sample size used was calculated using Yamane sample size formula which yielded sample size of 250.

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire consisting of two sections. Section A assessed the demographic profile of respondents while section B assessed the perception towards vaccine safety, consisting of 6 questions. The validity of the instrument was determined through face and content validity. A pilot test of the instrument was carried out with 10% of the calculated sample size, it was used to conduct and determine the reliability of the instrument which was ascertained using Cronbach alpha coefficient after administration of the instrument. The results of pilot study indicated an internal consistency as it has a coefficient value of 0.88.

Participants were informed about the pre-test/post-test questionnaire and how to complete it. Informed consent was obtained from the participants before they participated in the research. The pre-test questionnaire was distributed to the participants. The research assistants explained the instructions for completing the questionnaire and answered any questions that the participants had. Participants were given enough time to complete the questionnaire independently. Once the pre-test questionnaire had been completed, the research assistants collected it. After the pre-test questionnaire had been completed, the nurse-led interactive education session took place. The nurse provided information on their perception of COVID-19 vaccine. Once, the nurse-led interactive education session had been completed, the post-test questionnaire was distributed to the participants. The collected data was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics (independent sample t-test test) were used to analyse the data at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Socio demographic distribution of Participants

Variable		F(%)
Age	Less than 20yrs	-
	20-39yrs	164(69.5)
	40-59yrs	68(28.8)
	60yrs and above	4(1.7)
	Total	236(100)
	Mean age	30yrs \pm 0.503
Gender	Male	52(22)
	Female	184(78)
	Total	236(100)
Ethnicity	Hausa	16(6.8)
	Igbo	48(20.3)
	Yoruba	172(72.9)
	Total	236(100)
Religion	Christianity	176(74.6)
	Islam	60(25.4)
	Total	236(100)
Highest level of Education	RN only	60(25.4)
	BSC	172(72.9)
	MSC	-

	PhD	4(1.7)
	Total	236(100)

Table 1 delineates the socio-demographic profile of the respondents. A majority (69.5%) fell within the 20-39 age bracket, with females constituting 78% of the sample. Furthermore, over half (74%) identified as Yoruba, while a significant portion (74.6%) practiced Christianity. Moreover, the study revealed that the majority (72.9%) of respondents held a degree.

Table 2: Respondents Perceptions towards COVID-19 Vaccine

Items	Categories	Intervention [N=236]	
		Pre	Post
Have you received a COVID-19 vaccine	Yes	160(67.8%)	164(69.5)
	No	76(32.2%)	72(30.5)
If you answered "no" to question 1, what is the main reason you have not received a COVID-19 vaccine	I am concerned about the safety of the vaccine	12(5.1%)	4(1.7)
	I am not sure where to get a vaccine	-	8(3.4)
	I do not believe in vaccines	68(28.8%)	48(20.3)
	Others	4(1.7%)	8(3.4)
	Nil	152(64.4%)	168(71.2)
How would you rate your confidence in the safety and effectiveness of vaccines in general	Not confident at all	24(10.2%)	4(1.7)
	Some what unconfident	12(5.1%)	-
	Neutral	60(25.4%)	20(8.5)
	Somewhat confident	60(25.4%)	36(15.3)
	very confident	80(33.9%)	176(74.6)
How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "Vaccines are an important tool for preventing infectious diseases."	Strongly disagree	4(1.7%)	4(1.7)
	Neutral	4(1.7%)	4(1.7)
	Agree	8(3.4%)	20(8.5)
	Strongly agree	220(93.2%)	208(88.1)
How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "I trust the healthcare system to provide safe and effective vaccines	Strongly disagree	4(1.7%)	-
	Somewhat disagree	16(6.8%)	-
	Neutral	24(10.2%)	16(6.8)
	Agree	72(30.5%)	40(16.9)
	Strongly agree	120(50.8%)	180(76.3)
How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "I am concerned about the long-term effects of vaccines	Strongly disagree	12(5.1%)	44(18.6)
	Somewhat disagree	8(3.4%)	16(6.8)
	Neutral	8(3.4%)	24(10.2)
	Agree	96(40.7%)	48(20.3)
	Strongly agree	112(47.5%)	104(44.1)
How much do you agree or disagree with the following statement: "I would recommend vaccines to friends and family	Strongly disagree	16(6.8%)	-
	Somewhat disagree	8(3.4%)	4(1.7)
	Neutral	8(3.4%)	12(5.1)
	Agree	52(22.0%)	36(15.3)
	Strongly agree	152(64.4%)	184(78.0)
Have you ever experienced a negative side effect from a vaccine	Yes	156(66.1%)	184(78)
	No	80(33.9%)	52(22)
If you answered "yes" to question 8, how severe was the side effect	Mild	140(59.3%)	156(66.1)
	Moderate	68(28.8%)	52(22)
	Severe	28(11.9%)	28(11.9)
How much do you trust the information you receive from the media about vaccines	Not at all	4(1.7%)	24(10.2)
	Not very much	52(22%)	44(18.6)
	Neutral	40(16.9%)	52(22)
	Somewhat	88(37.3%)	56(23.7)
	A lot	52(22%)	60(25.4)

How much do you trust the information you receive from healthcare professionals about vaccines	Not very much	4(1.7%)	4(1.7)
	Neutral	20(8.5%)	8(3.4)
	Somewhat	88(37.3%)	28(11.9)
	A lot	124(52.5%)	196(83.1)
How likely are you to get a COVID-19 vaccine when it becomes available to you	very unlikely	16(6.8%)	-
	somewhat unlikely	24(10.2%)	-
	Neutral	12(5.1%)	8(3.4)
	somewhat likely	40(16.9%)	32(13.6)
	very likely	144(61.0%)	196(83.1)

Table 2 illustrates the changes in participants' responses regarding COVID-19 vaccines before and after the intervention. Following the intervention, a notable majority (69%) reported having received the COVID-19 vaccine, with 74.5% expressing heightened confidence in the safety and efficacy of the vaccine. Furthermore, post-intervention, 76.3% demonstrated trust in the healthcare system's capacity to deliver secure vaccines. Preceding the intervention, participants displayed reluctance toward COVID-19 vaccine acceptance. However, a positive transformation in perceptions was evident post-intervention, indicating a significant impact of the intervention on participants' attitudes toward COVID-19 vaccines.

Table 3: Summary of Respondents Perceptions towards COVID-19 Vaccine

Scores range	Level of perception	Pre-intervention	Post-intervention
		F(%)	F(%)
Less than 20	Poor	-	-
20-29	Fair	28(11.9%)	4(1.7)
30 and above	Good	208(88.1%)	232(98.3)
Total		236(100%)	236(100)
Mean±SD		36.7±5.03	38.9±3.63

Table 3 presents participants' perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine pre- and post-intervention. Before the intervention, the mean perception score in Lagos State was 36.8±5.03, which increased to 38.9±3.63 after the intervention. The table demonstrates an increase in participants holding positive perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine post-intervention. This indicates a rise in favorable perceptions and a decrease in neutral perceptions, suggesting the intervention's effectiveness.

Discussion

The intervention group demonstrated a significant improvement in their perception of vaccine safety. This finding highlights the effectiveness of the nurse-led interactive education program in addressing related to COVID-19 vaccine. It indicates that providing accurate and evidence-based information can positively impact nurses' perceptions, leading to increased confidence in vaccine safety. The study's findings are situated within the broader context of COVID-19 vaccine perceptions, drawing insights from various studies that explore these dynamics. Szilagyi et al. (2021) revealed that less than half of US parents expressed likelihood in having their children receive COVID-19 vaccines, emphasizing a significant hesitancy within this demographic. This skepticism is echoed by Sonmezer et al. (2022), who reported

that 62.7% of participants had positive perceptions of COVID-19 vaccines, indicating that a considerable proportion may hold reservations. In the healthcare context, Niznik et al. (2021) examined perceptions of COVID-19 vaccine safety and efficacy among frontline healthcare assistants (HCAs), emphasizing the importance of understanding perceptions within specific healthcare roles. Similarly, Janabi et al. (2021) focused on osteopathic medical students, recognizing the influential role of physicians' recommendations in vaccine acceptance. These studies collectively underscore the relevance of targeted interventions based on professional roles.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that the intervention program effectively influenced nurses' perceptions, enhancing their COVID-19 vaccination.

Recommendations

1. There is need to develop comprehensive programs, workshops, or training to address awareness of nurses towards COVID-19 vaccine acceptance.
2. The study highlights the need for increased investment in nurse-led educational interventions that equip nurses with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively communicate and address vaccine-related issue

References

- Blanchard, J.L., Johnson, C., McIntyre, M., Crowcroft, N.S., & Mclellan, A. (2018). A Pre And Post Intervention Study Measuring The Effect Of Interactive Education On Adolescent Perceptions Of Vaccines, Vaccine Safety And Disease Risk, *Journal Of Public Health* 5(6), 45-50
- Janabi, A., Noel, N.B., Nkala, J., & Mamza, R.B (2021). "Knowledge And Risk Perception Of Covid-19 And The Willingness To Take Covid-19 Vaccine Among Tertiary Institution Students In Jos, Plateau State: A Comparative Assessment Of Medical And Nursing Students", *Journal Of Epidemiological Society Of Nigeria*
- Nigeria center for disease control and prevention (NCDC, 2012): Visit NCDC website at [http:// www.ncdc.gov.ng](http://www.ncdc.gov.ng)
- Niznik, A., Ameerah M.N., Alshareef, Qattan,; Omar Alsharqi; Naseem A.I Rahahleh; Gowokani Chijere Chirwa; Mohammed Khaled Al-Hanawi, (2021). "Acceptability Of A Covid-19 Vaccine Among Healthcare Workers In The Kingdom Of Saudi Arabia", *Frontiers In Medicine*, 20-29
- Ogunrinde, M.E. & Gbenga-Epebinu, M.A (2020). Outcome of Health Education Intervention on the Knowledge of Management of Coronavirus Challenges in Ekiti State. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 7(9), 87 – 94. DOI: 10.14738/assrj.79.8966
- Osakinle, E.O, Babatunde, J.O., Ibimiluyi, F.O., Ogunkorode, A. & Gbenga-Epebinu, M.A (2021). The Role of Counselling in Management of Coronavirus. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science*, 3(6), 100 – 108. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5186475
- Shah, P.G., Thomas, K., M.D., Vizueta, N., Cui, Y., Sitaram V., Fox, C., & Kapteyn, A (2021). "The Role Of Trust In The Likelihood Of Receiving A Covid-19 Vaccine: Results From A National Survey", *Preventive Medicine*, 6, 76-82
- Sonmezer, M., Gudi, N., Nambiar, N., Dumka, N., Ahmed T., Isha, R. S., Kotwal, A. (2021). "A Rapid Review Of Evidence On The Determinants Of And Strategies For Covid-19

Vaccine Acceptance In Low- And Middle-Income Countries", *Journal Of Global Health* .3(2), 34-41

Szilagyi, S, Thomas, K., P.G., Vizueta, M.D., Cui, Y., Sitaram V., Fox, C., & Kapteyn, A (2021). "The Role Of Trust In The Likelihood Of Receiving A Covid-19 Vaccine: Results From A National Survey", *Preventive Medicine*, 6, 76-82

World Health Organization (WHO, 2023): <https://www.who.int> global updates, guidelines, and resources related to COVID-19 vaccines

Cite this article:

Author(s), NDURUE, Light Obioma (RN, MSN, OHSN, CPHN), OKAFOR, Ngozi Anthonia (RN, RM, RPHN, PhD), ABARIBE, Abaribe E. (RN, RM, RPHN, FWAPCNM, PhD), ABDULMALIK, Adams Adedayo (RN, RM, BNSc), (2024). "Effect of a Nurse-Led Interactive Education On Perceptions of Covid-19 Vaccine Among Nurses in Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos". **Name of the Journal:** Euro Global Contemporary Studies Journal, (EGCSJ.COM), P, 1-8. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060008> , Issue: 1, Vol.: 4, Article: 1, Month: February, Year: 2024. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

